

Studies on Some Schiff Base Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) Derived from Salicylaldehyde, Aminophenols and Anthranilic Acid

(Mrs.) P. R. SHUKLA, V. K. SINGH and A. M. JAISWAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

and

GOPAL NARAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar-470 003

Manuscript received 6 March 1981, revised 6 August 1982, accepted 28 January 1983

Schiff bases of the type salicylidene-*o*-aminophenol (o -C₁₁H₁₁O₂N), salicylidene-*m*-aminophenol (*m*-C₁₁H₁₁O₂N) and salicylideneanthranilic acid (C₁₄H₁₁O₂N) were prepared by reaction of salicylaldehyde with *o*- and *m*-aminophenol and anthranilic acid. The bases react with copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) sulphates to give neutral complexes of the type Cu or Ni(C₁₁H₁₁O₂N)(H₂O), Cu or Ni(C₁₄H₁₁O₂N)(H₂O), Co(C₁₁H₁₁O₂N) or Co(C₁₄H₁₁O₂N)(H₂O), which have been assigned planar and octahedral geometries on the basis of molar conductance, infrared, magnetic and electronic spectral data. The complexes undergo ligand replacement reactions with ammonia, pyridine, ethylene or propylenediamines to give new products which have also been characterised on the basis of analysis, TGA, magnetic and infrared data.

THE field of Schiff base complexes is fast developing on account of the wide variety of structures possible for the ligands depending upon the aldehydes and amines¹⁻³. The present study deals initially with the synthesis and characterisation of some complexes of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) with Schiff bases obtained by condensation of salicylaldehyde with aminophenols or anthranilic acid and subsequently the effect of ligand replacement reactions on these using ammonia, pyridine, ethylenediamine or propylenediamine as secondary ligand.

Experimental

The ligands used in the study possess the following general structure in which the deprotonation of the OH groups of salicylaldehyde and aminophenols as well as of the COOH group of anthranilic acid is

X = *o*- and *m*-OH or *o*-COOH

possible and hence they behave as bidentate and tridentate. They have been obtained by treating one mole of salicylaldehyde with one mole of the aminophenol or anthranilic acid in ethanol and crystallising out the product. On treatment with copper(II), nickel(II) or cobalt(II) sulphate, these ligands give green, yellow or pink complexes, the structures of which have been determined on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance,

magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data.

The molar conductances have been measured in nitrobenzene on a Philips PR 9500/90 type instrument. The magnetic moments and electronic spectra have been obtained by Gouy's method and in the form of nujol mulls on a Cary 14 instrument, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis show that only one molecule of the Schiff base is attached per molecule of the metal(II) ion (Table I) along with one or three molecules of water depending upon the metal ion. The presence of coordinated water is confirmed by TGA data where loss in weight corresponding to one water molecule for copper(II) and nickel(II) and three water molecules for cobalt(II) occurs at 280°.

The molar conductances of the complexes are in the range 0.5-1.2 mhos suggesting the neutral nature of the complexes. Hence the ligand, besides being coordinated to the metal(II) ion, also neutralises its charge. The formulae of the complexes are [Cu(L)(H₂O)], [Ni(L)(H₂O)] and [Co(L)(H₂O)₃]. The copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes are tetra-coordinated while the cobalt(II) is hexacoordinated. The site of coordination of the Schiff bases has been obtained by the infrared studies.

Infrared spectra: The free Schiff bases of aminophenols, (L₁), show the characteristic azome-

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, TGA AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF PARENT COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis% ; Found (Calcd.)				% loss of H ₂ O at 280°	μ_{eff} in (B.M.)
		M	C	H	N		
1. [Cu(o C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Green	21.20 (21.71)	54.40 (53.35)	4.02 (3.76)	5.10 (4.78)	5.28 (6.15)	1.88
2. [Ni(o-C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Yellow	20.94 (20.40)	54.68 (54.22)	4.18 (3.82)	5.32 (4.86)	6.00 (6.25)	1.28
3. [Co(o-C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Peach	18.19 (18.85)	48.15 (47.75)	4.63 (4.22)	4.32 (4.62)	17.95 (18.50)	5.13
4. [Cu(m-C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Dirty green	21.71 (21.31)	53.33 (54.01)	3.76 (4.08)	4.78 (5.00)	6.92 (6.15)	1.95
5. [Ni(m-C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Dark yellow	20.92 (20.47)	53.82 (54.17)	4.12 (3.81)	4.06 (4.78)	6.68 (6.25)	0.94
6. [Co(m-C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Light pink	18.19 (18.85)	48.15 (47.75)	4.63 (4.22)	4.32 (3.96)	17.82 (18.50)	Highly paramagnetic 2.01
7. [Cu(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Green	19.20 (19.81)	52.96 (52.41)	3.82 (3.43)	3.92 (4.32)	5.89 (5.61)	
8. [Ni(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Dark yellow	18.02 (18.59)	52.96 (53.21)	3.84 (3.48)	3.92 (4.43)	6.22 (5.70)	0.94
9. [Co(C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N)(H ₂ O)]	Pink	16.74 (16.20)	47.73 (48.20)	4.26 (4.86)	3.97 (4.66)	17.90 (18.95)	5.78

TABLE 2—ANALYSES, TGA AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF PRODUCTS OF REPLACEMENT REACTION

Complexes	Colour	% loss	Analysis % . Found (Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	N	
10. Cu(L _I)(NH ₃)	Green	—	21.78 (21.13)	9.60 (8.99)	1.90
11. [Cu(L ₂)(py)]	Green	—	17.96 (17.22)	7.92 (7.63)	1.92
12. [Cu(L ₁)(en)]	Dark brown	—	18.98 (18.24)	12.55 (12.92)	1.85
13. [Cu(L _I)(pn)]	Black	—	18.32 (18.84)	12.12 (11.92)	1.81
14. [Ni(L ₁)(NH ₃)	Brown	—	20.47 (21.02)	9.76 (9.07)	0.79
15. [Ni(L ₁)(py)]	Light brown	—	16.83 (16.23)	8.03 (8.56)	0.80
16. [Ni(L _I)(en)(H ₂ O)]	Brown	4.70 (5.19)	16.87 (16.22)	12.07 (11.82)	3.20
17. [Ni(L _I)(pn)(H ₂ O)]	Brown	5.45 (4.98)	16.22 (15.52)	11.61 (11.01)	3.42
18. [Co(L _I)(NH ₃)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Pink	11.62 (11.14)	18.25 (17.86)	8.67 (9.12)	5.32
19. [Co(L _I)(py)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Light pink	10.00 (9.33)	15.31 (16.01)	7.23 (7.92)	5.40
20. [Co(L _I)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Dirty pink	4.92 (5.18)	16.99 (17.50)	12.07 (12.52)	5.28
21. [Co(L _I)(pn)(H ₂ O)]	Pink	5.28 (4.97)	16.28 (15.82)	11.60 (12.01)	5.08
22. [Cu(L _{II})(NH ₃)	Green	—	19.86 (19.02)	8.76 (8.31)	1.95
23. [Cu(L _{II})(py)]	Green	—	16.64 (17.01)	7.33 (7.83)	1.82
24. [Cu(L _{II})(en)]	Bottle green	—	17.51 (17.82)	11.58 (11.98)	1.90
25. [Cu(L _{II})(pn)]	Black	—	16.95 (17.42)	11.21 (11.98)	1.85
26. [Ni(L _{II})(NH ₃)	Yellow	—	18.70 (18.12)	8.89 (8.67)	0.75
27. [Ni(L _{II})(py)]	Yellowish brown	—	15.64 (15.12)	7.43 (7.82)	0.72
28. [Ni(L _{II})(en)(H ₂ O)]	Dirty yellow	5.02 (4.79)	15.62 (16.20)	11.18 (11.80)	3.15
29. [Ni(L _{II})(pn)(H ₂ O)]	Brown	4.95 (4.62)	15.06 (14.62)	10.79 (11.02)	3.22
30. [Co(L _{II})(NH ₃)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Pink	10.08 (9.80)	16.79 (16.42)	7.77 (7.68)	5.01
31. [Co(L _{II})(py)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Pink	9.10 (8.33)	14.62 (14.12)	6.94 (7.05)	5.05
32. [Co(L _{II})(en)(H ₂ O)]	Light brick red	5.65 (4.78)	16.28 (16.68)	7.73 (8.02)	5.40
33. [Co(L _{II})(pn)(H ₂ O)]	Light brick red	4.20 (4.81)	15.67 (16.01)	7.44 (6.98)	5.18

L_I = Schiff base of salicylaldehyde + o-aminophenol
 L_{II} = Schiff base of salicylaldehyde + anthranilic acid
 py = Pyridine
 en = ethylenediamine
 pn = propylenediamine

thine and OH frequencies at 1660 and 3500 cm^{-1} , respectively. The former shifts to around 1610 cm^{-1} in the complexes due to coordination, while the νOH band disappears showing that it has been deprotonated. In the Schiff bases of anthranilic acid, (L_{II}), the azomethine and carboxylic frequencies are observed at 1645 and 1550 cm^{-1} which shift lower in complexes showing the involvement of both the groups in coordination⁴⁻⁹. The presence of coordinated water in all the complexes is indicated by a sharp band around 3460 cm^{-1} and two somewhat weaker bands around 860 and 700 cm^{-1} assigned as the OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations, respectively.

The magnetic and electronic spectral studies confirm the geometries of the complexes as follows.

Copper(II) complexes : The μ_{eff} values of complexes are in the range of 1.95-2.36 B.M. indicative of square planar geometry. In confirmation of this structure only one band is seen in the spectra around 700 nm with two shoulders on either side at 540 nm and 880 nm. These are assigned to ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transitions, respectively with Dq value of 1430 cm^{-1} .

Nickel(II) complexes : The complexes possess magnetic moments between 0.94-1.24 B.M. As these values are much lower than the spin only value, a planar structure is proposed for the complexes. The development of paramagnetism on six and five coordinated nickel(II) complexes in solution is very common but its presence in the present tetracoordinated complexes in the solid state, although rare, may either be due to the presence of nickel(II) in the tetrahedral environment or due to spin cross over phenomenon. To distinguish between the two, low temperature magnetic studies have been made on the complexes but no distinct change in the value is seen.

Complexes	μ_{eff} at 303K	μ_{eff} at 257K	μ_{eff} at 143K
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	1.24 B.M.	1.18 B.M.	1.20 B.M.
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	0.99 B.M.	0.95 B.M.	1.05 B.M.

This observation rules out the presence of tetrahedral-geometry or T ground term in the complexes, for which the μ_{eff} values decrease sharply with decreasing temperature. The partial paramagnetism is therefore due to the spin cross over from singlet to triplet state. It has been reported that under certain exceptional circumstances involving steric deformations, the transition from the diamagnetic to the paramagnetic state does not require much energy and hence becomes possible even in the solid state¹⁰⁻¹³. If the spin only value of 2.89 B.M. is taken as reference, it appears that only 40% of nickel(II) is present in the triplet state and even in the cross over effect it is the planar form which tends to be more stable. The same is supported by the spectra which is typical of a planar complex with two bands around 600 and 400 nm. These are due to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$ (ν_3) and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively. In some complexes another weak band

(ν_1) appears at 800 nm. The Dq values are around 1700 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of a strong ligand field.

Cobalt(II) complexes : These complexes are hexacoordinated with μ_{eff} values of 5.46-5.97 B.M., suggesting octahedral structure. The electronic spectra confirm the structure as two main bands centered around 500 nm and 1310 nm are seen corresponding to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ (ν_3) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_1) transitions, respectively. The third or the ν_2 band due to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ transition is seen at 610 nm. The ν_3 band is split in all the complexes in two components one at 410 nm and the other at 460 nm. The Dq and β values are in the usual octahedral range. These spectra, therefore, justify the assignment of pseudo octahedral structure for complexes, the lowering in symmetry being due to the presence of mixed ligand field.

Replacement reactions : Some of the complexes of Schiff bases of *o*-aminophenol and anthranilic acid were treated with the required amount of methanolic solutions of ammonia, pyridine, ethylenediamine, propylenediamine and the solution refluxed for 4-5 hr. The resulting compound was isolated by repeated crystallisation from petroleum ether. The formulae of the complexes have been assigned on the basis of percentages of metal and nitrogen and the infrared spectra have been recorded to show that substitution has actually taken place.

The following illustrates the type of reaction carried out on the parent complexes along with its product :

It is evident that during the replacement reaction the Schiff base moieties remain intact in the products which also show the characteristic relevant vibrations in the infrared spectra, as in the parent complexes. For copper(II) complexes all the amines used replace water molecules completely and νOH disappears, while for cobalt(II) complexes, the use of mono or bidentate amine replaces one or two water molecules (as shown by the TGA data) with the νOH still at 3450 cm^{-1} . For nickel(II) complexes, however, ammonia and pyridine replace the single water molecule (νOH disappears) but ethylenediamine and propylenediamine get attached as such without replacing water (νOH at 3450 cm^{-1}). The coordination of ammonia, ethylene- or propylenediamine in the products is indicated by the NH vibrations at 3250 cm^{-1} , while that of pyridine by the positive shifts of C=C and ring stretching vibrations¹⁴.

It is further seen that the magnetic moments of all copper(II) and cobalt(II) complexes and also the

nickel(II) complexes of ammonia and pyridine are in the same range as parents and hence no change in the geometry of these complexes occurs on replacement.

The magnetic moments of nickel(II) complexes of ethylene- or propylenediamines are around 3.20 B.M., characteristic of two unpaired electrons. It thus appears that these complexes take up the additional ligands and change to a high spin octahedral structure. This change of geometry for a planar nickel(II) complex is well known and possible because of the strong tendency of the ion to attain the stable octahedral structure.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A. M. J.) is thankful to Dr. K. Singh and Sri S. P. Shukla, Lecturer in Chemistry, B. S. N. V. Degree College, Lucknow for their cooperation.

References

1. H. KREBS, H. STRACK and K. PACHALY, *Allg. Chem.*, 1971, **38**, 80.
2. Y. NAKAO and A. NAKAHARA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1973, **46**, 187.
3. L. A. ZYZYCK, H. PREMMER and J. F. VILLA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1653.
4. M. N. SAHA and B. N. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 10.
5. S. SATPATHY and B. SAHA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 188.
6. D. N. SEN, S. NISUSHIMA, C. CURRAN and J. V. QUALIANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 211.
7. Y. H. DESHPANDE and V. RAMCHANDRA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 1051.
8. M. N. STIMSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1954, **22**.
9. M. DAVIES and R. L. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 121.
10. J. B. WILLS and D. P. MELLOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 123.
11. CALVIN and WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
12. LIFSCHILZ and DIJKENS, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1939, **97**, 242.
13. D. P. MELLOR and LOCKWOOD, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1940, **74**, 141.
14. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTOLI and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.